

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

AI AND BLOCKCHAIN FOR NEUROPSYCHOLOGY

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Abstract

Advances in neuropsychology, along with other neuroscience, serve as a basis for the development of artificial intelligence systems. Meanwhile, there is the opposite direction of research on the use of artificial intelligence in neuropsychology. This article examines the possibilities of artificial intelligence in alliance with blockchain in neuropsychological diagnostics and the analysis of its results.

Keywords: neuropsychology, neuropsychological diagnostics, artificial intelligence, blockchain.

The development of artificial intelligence (AI) systems is driven not only by technological advances, but also by developments in neuroscience.

The interdisciplinary science of neuropsychology was formed in response to the needs of clinical practice and education. The foundations of neuropsychology were laid in the 1920s and 40s at the intersection of psychology, neurophysiology, and medicine. The main merit in creating neuropsychology as an independent branch of psychology belongs to A.R. Luria, however, the first neuropsychological studies were conducted as early as by L.S. Vygotsky, an outstanding pedagogue. The task of neuropsychology was to investigate the connection between local brain lesions and disorders of mental processes, as well as to improve the efficiency of the healthy brain. Neuropsychology is indispensable for solving problems of teaching children with special educational needs related to disabilities; organization of inclusive education and solving problems of increasing effectiveness and accessibility of education for all; verification of theoretical foundations of used teaching methods and their improvement from the point of view of correspondence to the laws of brain functioning and psychophysiological features and abilities of a child. Neuropsychology makes it possible to understand the brain bases of a student's individuality, to find the causes of his or her academic difficulties and effective ways of overcoming them, to build optimal educational routes and avoid mistakes in choosing a professional orientation. For teachers, neuropsychology provides a wide range of techniques for effective instruction and individualization. Where teachers apply the knowledge of neuropsychology, the quality of learning improves, children are less tired, and the risks of developing chronic emotional stress, which, in turn, provokes psychosomatic disorders, are reduced [1].

Neuropsychological knowledge is in demand in clinical research (clinical neuropsychology) for rehabilitation of patients with brain traumas and diseases: strokes, craniocerebral injuries); in forensic examination; in directions of industry where neuropsychological knowledge is necessary for product development.

The subject of research in neuropsychology is the systemicity of the dynamic organization of mental functions on the basis of the methodology of factor analysis of loss of functions with the use of methods of syndromic analysis. Neuropsychological diagnostic complexes have been developed to determine the functional activity of different brain areas, which allow to map the brain, identify problem areas and develop programs to help children.

Neuropsychology is closely connected with the cognitive sciences (cognitive psychology), psychiatry and computer science - especially in the creation of artificial neural networks.

Artificial intelligence is a broad field of computer science in which computers learn to model the process of thinking, learning, and perception as in humans.

The term "artificial intelligence" has been in use since 1956, but only in recent years has it seen a major shift, with the advent of Deep Learning, machine learning, that is, machine learning.

Neuropsychology and artificial intelligence research have a long history together. These are discoveries in the field of computer modeling, based on the principles of the brain, its structure and functions, the method of error back propagation, the ability to solve nonlinear problems, error calculation in deep learning, learning with reinforcement, understanding and modeling of information processing in the brain. These are the teachings of A. Luria about the three blocks of the brain, coordinated feedback, anticipatory reflection in coding information, learning based on Hebb's rules, algorithms of attention formation.

Today, artificial intelligence can perform some of the tasks that neuropsychology traditionally did: to determine the features of human perception, analyze schoolwork and identify problem areas of the brain, to create individual lessons to overcome learning difficulties, to be a tutor. AI can identify students with tendencies to socially dangerous and destructive behavior by analyzing their written work [4].

Artificial intelligence can automate knowledge assessment. It is possible that AI will learn to fully check

written work and examinations based on established criteria, which will eliminate the bias or incompetence of teachers. AI will recognize and assess how students react to different topics and assignments, which will help teachers identify students' strengths and weaknesses and analyze their emotional and physical state.

Artificial intelligence can significantly increase the efficiency of the education system, personalize the learning process in accordance with the individual needs of students, reduce the administrative burden on teachers. AI will make it possible to identify students' learning deficits and select remedial tasks. This does not mean that AI will replace the teacher, because the learning process is subjective in nature, as a process of human involvement in culture and its reproduction. Through human cooperation with artificial intelligence, rather than replacing the teacher with a machine, the educational process will become more ergonomic, comfortable, of high quality, and accessible to all [2].

Born on the basis of the successes of neuroscience, AI itself becomes their tool, and not only in the applied dimension, but also in neurotheory. AI makes it possible to predict patterns of neuroactivity, decode neuroimaging data, classify brain disorders, act as a diagnostic tool, even create the basis for computational psychiatry.

It is possible that in the future AI will be able to solve individual diagnostic tasks of practical neurodiagnostics concerning the state of visual, auditory, tactile and kinesthetic perception; inter-analyzer connections; sensor-motor coordination; profile of lateral brain organization; spatial orientations; attention and memory; preferred cognitive styles of information processing, coding and transformation; self-regulation styles, etc. In the human-machine system, the results obtained can become the basis for the development of subject-oriented individual training programs with neurocorrective functions. Since neuropsychological diagnostic complexes are associated with obtaining a huge amount of personal information, which must be updated several times per academic year, collated, accumulated and year after year, i.e. to work with big data for many years, there is a need to combine AI with blockchain technology. This is a technology that allows to accumulate in an unchanged form virtually unlimited amount of information and guarantee its complete confidentiality [1].

In addition to the issue of the confidentiality of obtained "deep" knowledge about the human brain, the problem of the limits of its intrusion also appears.

The problems of neuroethics are the domain of bioethics. It answers the questions: what is good and what is bad about invading and manipulating the human brain. With the growth of technical possibilities of interfering with the brain, understanding the neural basis of behavior, personality, consciousness there are questions related to the problem of violence against the person, confidentiality of information about the person, propensity for crime, about the person's abilities and his

health. Brain invasion also has a broad philosophical context: to what extent can we influence free will, personal identity, human choices. To what extent can we interfere with how people think, feel? Does a person have the right to "cognitive freedom"? In what areas of neuroscience use are dangers lurking? Many problems arise from speculation about the successes of neuroscience, the direct transfer of the results of electroencephalography, magnetic resonance imaging, computer and positron emission tomography of the brain to the behavioral level. For example, training at the alpha level, based on stimulating waves of brain activity with light and sound, has been proposed to increase memorization ability; the use of neuroimplants, devices implanted in the skull cavity that are used to control or regulate brain activity not for therapeutic purposes, but for healthy individuals to improve their learning, is also an issue. Implants can also affect neighboring areas of the brain, changing a person's behavior. If this leads to negative consequences, who is legally and morally responsible for them? [3]

Conclusion.

The alliance of neuropsychology with AI and blockchain seems promising for both the development of AI systems and the theory and practice of neuropsychology. The realization of the great opportunities opened up by such a partnership is not only in the plane of science, but also has a philosophical and ethical character, raising the problems of human safety and health.

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